

Blue Water MPAs: Developing a Shared Research Agenda

January 21-22, 2019 | Meeting Proceedings
Cavallo Point, Sausalito, CA

Blue Water MPAs: Developing a Shared Research Agenda
Meeting Proceedings

CONTENTS

SUMMARY 3

BACKGROUND 3

CONTEXT AND ASSUMPTIONS..... 3

RESEARCH AGENDA..... 4

 Fisheries 4

 Biodiversity..... 4

 Resilience..... **Error! Bookmark not defined.**

 Human Dimensions 5

 Cross-Cutting 6

NEXT STEPS..... 6

APPENDIX A | Meeting Participants 7

APPENDIX B | Meeting Agenda 8

APPENDIX C | What Is a Blue Water Marine Protected Area? 10

APPENDIX D | Presentations Given During the Workshop..... 11

APPENDIX E | Examples of possible threats BWMPAs could address 12

APPENDIX F | Meeting Pre-read materials..... 13

SUMMARY

On January 21-22, 2019, The Nature Conservancy (TNC) and Conservation International (CI) convened a group of experts and collaborators to co-create a shared research agenda for Blue Water Marine Protected Areas (BWMPAs).¹ The purpose of the meeting was to identify gaps in scientific evidence relating to the impacts (+/-) of BWMPAs and to develop and prioritize a set of research priorities to address those gaps. This document, prepared by California Environmental Associates (who served as the meeting facilitators), summarizes the main takeaways from the two day meeting, including the draft research agenda that meeting participants developed together and relevant meeting materials.

BACKGROUND

Governments, philanthropic institutions, and nonprofit organizations continue to invest significantly in BWMPAs. However, gaps remain in the scientific evidence surrounding the impact BWMPAs can have and how to realize their greatest potential as conservation tools. The impetus behind the *Blue Water MPAs: Developing a Shared Research Agenda* meeting was to recognize the momentum around BWMPAs and the importance of establishing evidence and data that can be used to guide decision making around BWMPAs moving forward. Our overarching objective is to guide efforts to realize the potential conservation and economic benefits of BWMPAs, and under what conditions those benefits are likely to accrue. Developing a shared research agenda will help to coordinate and direct finite resources to fill priority knowledge gaps ultimately ensuring that we use and design BWMPAs to reach their highest potential.

CONTEXT AND ASSUMPTIONS

At the outset of the meeting, the group outlined several working “assumptions.” Assumptions spanned various topics, clarified terms, and defined the scope of the group’s purpose.

- A significant number of BWMPAs currently exist and momentum is growing to establish more BWMPAs. We need to conduct research and gather the necessary data that will allow us to make recommendations on design and the value of the approach. Where possible, our research agenda should be informed by the needs of decision makers and key stakeholders.
- MPAs and fisheries management are tools in a larger toolbox to conserve biodiversity and sustain ocean resources. Both are critical to ocean conservation and it is important to use them in a complementary manner for biodiversity and fisheries, understanding the strengths and weaknesses of each approach.
- Interest in understanding the human dimensions of BWMPAs has grown in recent years. Much of this momentum has stemmed from Big Ocean’s 2016 “Think Tank” on Human Dimensions which identified priority topics for future research. At the outset, the group recognized the excellent work of the Big Ocean group and intentionally didn’t go into detail on the human dimensions piece of BWMPAs. This was in part because of the expertise of workshop

¹ A definition of Blue Water MPAs can be found in Appendix C. For the purposes of the two day meeting, BWMPAs were defined as large, no-take, open ocean MPAs.

participants (biophysical, economics) and because of the robust community of practice already working on these issues.

- The value of MPAs shouldn't be tied primarily to fisheries outcomes. We need to think about other benefits related to a wide range of outcomes.
- BWMPA impacts should be considered at multiple scales, including inside and outside MPA boundaries.
- Given the unknown nature of current and future ocean threats, applying the precautionary principal is warranted (See Appendix E for "Examples of possible threats BWMPAs could address," which was developed by a small breakout group during the meeting). That being said, it is also important to design BWMPAs in service of specific objectives where possible.
- BWMPAs are not a panacea. They are well suited to address certain ocean conservation objectives and threats, not all.

RESEARCH AGENDA

During the meeting, meeting attendees worked in plenary and small groups to identify existing knowledge and research gaps on the impacts of BWMPAs. Knowledge gaps fell into three topical categories: *fisheries, biodiversity & resilience, and human dimensions*. Additionally several cross-cutting issues were identified. The group used the following criteria to determine priorities: strategic relevance (i.e. urgency, transferability) and feasibility (i.e. answerability and cost). Together, the group honed in on a priority list of research questions, below.

Biodiversity & Resilience

A few key themes emerged relative to the role that BWMPAs could play relative to biodiversity and resilience, including protection of intact open ocean ecosystems, conservation of highly migratory species, and climate change mitigation and adaptation. Specific research questions included:

- When can a BWMPA confer ecological resilience to anthropogenic threats?
 - How do threats cause fundamental changes in key ecosystem state variables for the pelagic ecosystem: Biogeochemical cycling, habitat change, trophic structure, and extinction risk?
 - Relevant to ecosystem state and function: Critical biophysical (e.g., pelagic features such as upwelling cells, thermal fronts, eddies) and biological features (e.g., demography and dispersal)
 - How do BWMPAs abate key threats (e.g., climate change impacts) on pelagic systems?
- Can BWMPAs contribute to the conservation of species and biota of conservation concern?
 - What are the relevant indicators of biodiversity for assessing the impacts of BWMPAs for different objectives (e.g., social, cultural, intrinsic, ecological)?
- Which paradigm of BWMPA protected area network design (e.g., representation, EBSAs, or process models, KBAs) delivers the great resilience in an uncertain future (e.g., impacts of climate change, new extractive industries such as deep sea mining)? How do the different paradigms compare in

terms of achieving resilience; what combination is most effective for BWMPA conservation planning?

- Under different scenarios of uncertainty (high, low), which approach is the most effective?
- Need to consider practical reality of which paradigms are being used, at what scale
- How do you define representation in the open ocean? How much representative habitat should you protect?
- How would you develop a bioregional approach that takes into account different pelagic ecosystem types and functions? How does vertical connectivity (e.g. sea floor to surface) and temporal and horizontal spatial stability fit into a bioregionalization?
- What is currently protected by current MPAs? Considering the current landscape of BWMPAs, are they representative? What are the biggest gaps? How do we fill the gaps?
- Assuming a system of BWMPAs will be designed via process models (models that optimize design for specific objectives), what are the big questions that need to be answered?
- Assuming a system of BWMPAs will be designed via EBSAs, what are the big questions that need to be answered?

Fisheries

Key themes related to fisheries outcomes and blue water MPAs that were discussed at the meeting included: evidence of spillover effects, effectiveness of BWMPAs at reducing overfishing and/or increasing fish abundance, and impacts of BWMPAs on fishery profitability, economic performance, etc.

- Under what conditions do BWMPAs:
 - Increase overall abundance/biomass?
 - Affect overall catch (e.g. rate, composition)?
 - Reduce the risk of overfishing?
 - Address local depletion issues?
 - Affect the spatial and temporal distribution of fisheries resources (e.g. benefits in EEZs and nearshore)?
 - Impact fishery profitability and the distribution of those profits?
- How do fleet dynamics and institutional dynamics affect outcomes for BWMPAs?
- Would an international commitment to establish BWMPAs in a certain percentage of the ocean protect against overfishing in low-governance countries?

Human Dimensions

The group recognized the excellent work of the Big Ocean's 2016 "Think Tank" on Human Dimensions to identify priority topics for future research and, as such, intentionally didn't go into detail on the human dimensions piece of BWMPAs. However, a few questions emerged that are not represented in that agenda that the group thought were important.

- Are there other human dimension impacts and distribution questions associated with BWMPAs that are not covered in the Big Ocean Human Dimensions research agenda (Christie et al. 2017)?

- E.g., under what conditions would a declaration of whole EEZ management deliver positive impacts?
- What are the appropriate measures of equity with respect to BWMPA design and management?
- What are the socioeconomic impacts and benefits of BWMPAs?
 - What are the economic costs and benefits of BWMPAs and how are they distributed?
 - How do BWMPAs impact fishery profitability and distribution of those profits?
 - How do BWMPAs impact food security?

Cross-Cutting

- What are the design attributes (e.g., biological, social, ecological) that determine the effectiveness of BWMPAs for different objectives (e.g., economic, food security, resilience)?
 - Do lessons from nearshore environments transfer to BWMPAs or do we need new theory?
 - What is the role of new technology in measuring the efficacy of BW MPAs?
- What key BWMPA design features determine effectiveness (for different objectives) in different ecosystems (e.g. temperate, polar, tropical)?

NEXT STEPS

During the final session of the workshop, meeting participants discussed several next steps and possible paths forward:

- 1) **Finalize and communicate the research agenda externally:**
 - a. Develop a public version of the BWMPA shared research agenda (e.g., a white paper). Including appropriate context and a synthesis of the meeting and the research agenda and with the objective of sharing it with funders.
 - b. Publish research agenda in a peer-reviewed journal. Develop a shorter version of the research agenda that could be published in a peer-reviewed journal.
 - c. Share the research agenda at global policy forums (e.g., CBD).
 - d. Engage invitees who weren't able to attend; ask for input on meeting outputs.
- 2) **Seek additional funding:**
 - a. For research projects: Develop concept notes for important research projects and share with funders.
 - b. For ongoing coordination of this group and its research efforts: Develop a proposal for funding that would support additional meetings, coordination, and research support to drive the research agenda forward (e.g., SNAPP, or other funders).

TNC and CI (with support from others, like CEA), will work with participants to put a detailed workplan together based on the next steps listed above, including leads and timelines for each task.

Appendix A | Meeting Participants

	Name	Organization
1	Johann Bell	Conservation International
2	Kristina Boerder	Dalhousie University (<i>participated by phone</i>)
3	Jorge Brenner	The Nature Conservancy
4	Meg Caldwell	Packard Foundation
5	Christopher Costello	The University of California Santa Barbara
6	Ginny Farmer	Conservation International
7	Eddie Game	The Nature Conservancy
8	Melissa Garvey	The Nature Conservancy
9	Leah Gerber	Arizona State University
10	Barry Gold	Walton Family Foundation (<i>participated by phone</i>)
11	Ray Hilborn	The University of Washington
12	Jack Kittinger	Conservation International & Arizona State University
13	Jake Kritzer	Environmental Defense Fund
14	Amanda Nickson	Pew Charitable Trusts
15	Dan Ovando	University of Washington
16	Hugh Possingham	The Nature Conservancy
17	Matt Rand	Pew Charitable Trusts
18	Anthony Richardson	CSIRO & University of Queensland
19	John Sibert	University of Hawaii (Emeritus)
20	Mike Sweeney	The Nature Conservancy
21	'Aulani Wilhelm	Conservation International
22	Tim White	Stanford University
23	Mark Zimring	The Nature Conservancy

Invited but unable to attend:

Julia Blanchard	Institute of Marine and Antarctic Studies, University of Tasmania
Chuck Cook	The Nature Conservancy
Alan Friedlander	National Geographic & University of Hawaii @ Manoa
Steve Gaines	The University of California Santa Barbara
Ben Halpern	University of California at Santa Barbara
John Hampton	Pacific Community (SPC)
Denny Kelso	Moore Foundation
Jane Lubchenco	Oregon State University
Doug McCauley	University of California at Santa Barbara
Callum Roberts	University of York
Enric Sala	National Geographic
Boris Worm	Dalhousie University

Appendix B | Meeting Agenda

Blue Water MPAs: Building a Shared Research Agenda
 Hosted by Conservation International and the Nature Conservancy
 Cavallo Point, 601 Murray Cir, Sausalito CA
 January 21-22, 2019

Monday, January 21st

Towards a Shared Understanding of Where We Are

8:15 – 8:45 am	Breakfast	Facilitators
8:45 – 9:10 am	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop objectives, context, potential outputs and next steps (Mark and Jack) Review ground rules for meeting (CEA) 	Mark Zimring Jack Kittinger CEA
9:10 – 9:30 am	Group Introductions	All
9:30 – 11:30 am	<u>Setting the Stage</u> Blue Water MPAs definition and intended objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief overview of session (Eddie and Aulani 10 min) BWMPA overview (Eddie 15 min ppt, 15 min discussion) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BWMPAs defined broadly and for the purposes of this meeting (location, size, drivers, protection levels) Range of BWMPA objectives: fisheries impacts, endangered species focus, ocean wilderness, etc. Blue water MPA trends (Aulani 15 min ppt, 15 min discussion) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trends and proliferation of Blue Water MPAs Global conservation targets Group discussion: What are the intended objectives that we hope that BWMPAs will deliver and key challenges? (Eddie and Aulani 50 min) 	'Aulani Wilhelm Eddie Game
11:30 – 11:45	Break	
11:45 – 12:30 pm	Lunch	
12:30 – 2:45 pm	<u>Identify Knowledge Gaps</u> What do we know and not know about the impacts of BWMPAs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review strawman list of hypotheses typically associated with BWMPA impacts – seek input from the group: Should we add/delete any from the list? (15 min) Brief presentations synthesizing current research and knowledge gaps in three key issue areas (45 min total – 15 min each) 	Chris Costello Ray Hilborn Hugh Possingham

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Value of information Theory (Hugh) ○ Biodiversity and Blue Water MPAs (Ray) ○ Fisheries benefits and impacts (Chris) ○ Sociocultural impacts ('Aulani) ● Breakout groups each discuss a key issue area listed above (45 mins): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is currently well covered by literature/knowledge? ○ What are the key areas of uncertainty and knowledge gaps? ● Breakout groups present back to full group (30 mins total/10 min each) 	
2:45 – 3 pm	Break	
3 – 4 pm	<u>Prioritize Research Gaps</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Group exercise to prioritize research gaps surfaced in earlier discussion 	CEA
6 pm	Dinner @ Cavallo Point	

Tuesday, January 22nd

Towards a Prioritized Research Agenda

8:15 – 9:00 am	Breakfast	Facilitators
9 – 9:15 am	Day 1 synthesis and reflections	Meg Caldwell
9:15 – 9:30 am	Review plan for Day 2	Mark Zimring Jack Kittinger
9:30 – 12:15 pm	<u>How Do We Fill Key Knowledge Gaps?</u> Outline a shared research agenda for Blue Water MPAs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Acquisition of empirical data ● Modeling approaches ● Technology 	Jake Kritzer Anthony Richardson
12:15 – 12:30 pm	Break	
12:30 – 1:15 pm	Lunch	
1:15 – 4 pm	<u>Finalize the research agenda and next steps</u> Prioritize/characterize research agenda based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Importance, Cost, Timeline, Feasibility of filling gaps/answer questions; ● Do any specific projects rise to the top? 	CEA
4 – 4:15 pm	Break	
4:15 – 5 pm	Wrap-Up & Closing	Mark Zimring Jack Kittinger

APPENDIX C | What Is a Blue Water Marine Protected Area?

Blue Water MPA definition

Blue water refers to open ocean ecosystems, and the species associated with them. Open ocean ecosystems are in contrast to coastal marine ecosystems, those adjacent to land including small islands. Open ocean ecosystems are primarily pelagic and tend to be dominated by physical, chemical and biological features that are highly dynamic in space and time, but there are likely strong connections between the pelagic and benthic components of these ecosystems. There are also likely strong connections between open ocean ecosystems and island and shallow reef ecosystems, and in many cases the designation of blue water MPAs is catalyzed by these islands. However, island ecosystems are not the focus of this meeting. Neither “blue water” nor “open-ocean” is a geopolitical definition and these ecosystems include both high seas and waters inside national jurisdiction.

A blue water **marine protected area** (MPA) in our definition refers to a spatially defined area of open ocean explicitly dedicated to the protection and maintenance of marine biodiversity, ecosystems and associated cultural resources, and is managed for this purpose. MPAs are primarily a tool to manage where different activities can occur and while our definition does not restrict consideration to ‘no-take’ MPAs, the intent of the MPAs must be to limit the occurrence of extractive, destructive and polluting activities inside its boundaries. In the open ocean, fishing represents the most common activity excluded by blue water MPAs. Spatial management measures are sometimes used in the open ocean as a tool to manage stocks of target species, such as fisheries time and area closures. We only consider these blue water MPAs where the objectives for the closure extend beyond managing the commercial species to include conservation of non-target blue water biodiversity.

Blue water MPAs does not explicitly mean large MPAs, however, open ocean ecosystems are the largest contiguous ecosystems on the planet and this is often reflected in the size of blue water MPA designations. Similarly, countries that have committed to placing 10% of their marine habitats in protected areas under the Convention on Biological Diversity will necessarily include large areas of open ocean habitat – *blue water MPAs*.

APPENDIX D | Presentations Given During the Workshop

Below is a list of the presentations that were given during the workshop (copies of the presentations are included as attachments to this document):

- Setting the Stage: Blue Water MPAs definition and intended objectives | Eddie Game and 'Aulani Wilhelm
- Brief presentations synthesizing current research and knowledge gaps in three key issue areas:
 - Biodiversity and Blue Water MPAs | Ray Hillborn
 - Fisheries benefits and impacts | Chris Costello
 - Sociocultural impacts | 'Aulani Wilhelm

APPENDIX E | Examples of possible threats BWMPAs could address

Threat	Information for blue waters
Seafloor mining	P mining (NZ, Namibia) + Peak P Methane hydrates for natural gas (biggest reserve) Hydrothermal vents for Au, Ag, Cu, Mn, Co, Zn
Fishing	Likely effects on higher trophic levels
Fishing myctophids	Mesopelagic fisheries are likely to increase in the future
Climate change	Magnitude and “direction” changes with depth
Ocean acidification	Magnitude changes with depth
Microplastics	
Seismic surveys	Effects on marine mammals and fish Effects on zooplankton? Increases mortality from 19% to 45% up to 1.2 km away (McCauley et al. 2017)
Shipping	Ship strikes for cetaceans Boat-generated turbulence (Bickel et al. 2011) – Zooplankton mortality 5% vs 34% in high traffic Mortality caused by spills
Geosequestration	Iron fertilization Fertilization from depth

Conservation Impacts of Blue Water Marine Protected Areas

A rapid assessment of relevant literature and hypotheses

Introduction

This document summarizes findings from a rapid scan of the literature in the blue water MPA space, with a focus on three primary conservation impacts: biodiversity, fisheries, and human dimensions. A final section focuses on blue water MPA design, governance, and management considerations. This is *not* a comprehensive literature review or full catalogue of existing empirical evidence, but rather an overview of major themes and hypotheses identified in key publications. The purpose of this document is to provide a quick summary and overview and is meant to spark productive thinking and discussion. We have also included summaries of other relevant blue water MPA research agendas in an Appendix I, including those developed by Big Ocean Managers, a network of blue water MPA management professionals and practitioners (Big Ocean Planning Team 2013), and a human dimensions think tank (Christie et al 2017). We expect these materials to provide a baseline, which workshop participants can use as a starting point in defining a shared research agenda during our meeting on January 21st-22nd.

Background

Governments, nonprofit organizations, and philanthropic foundations have invested significantly in the establishment of blue water marine protected areas (i.e., those primarily focused on protecting open ocean habitats and species). While a wealth of scientific and policy expertise on coastal marine protected areas (MPAs) has been developed, far less is known about the potential conservation and social impacts of blue water MPAs, and under what conditions benefits and costs are likely to accrue. As such, demonstrating the impact, and therefore effectiveness, of blue water MPAs remains an important priority for the marine conservation and management community. However, empirical studies have been limited, with more emphasis on hypothesized rather than realized outcomes (Davies et al. 2018). This in part because:

1. Data is limited due to challenges of accessing remote and deep areas of the open ocean (Big Ocean 2013) and the fact that creation of MPAs generally means losing fishing records, one of the main sources of data on open ocean environments.
2. Expected changes in ecosystems and the location and time frame on which they will occur is often uncertain, especially for open ocean ecosystems with large vertical and horizontal footprints and high levels of connectivity (Levin et al. 2016; O’Leary and Roberts 2018).
3. There is uncertainty about key features and complexities of open ocean species and ecosystems (Game et al. 2009).

Despite these challenges, there is still good reason to believe that well-designed blue water MPAs can be effective at protecting pelagic ecosystems and species, reducing cumulative impacts for a wide array of threats, and returning social and ecological benefits (Game et al. 2009; Koldewey et al. 2010). The ocean conservation community’s current and future interests and investments in blue water MPAs make this an opportune time to identify key knowledge gaps and start the process of developing a prioritized list of research questions and hypotheses around the environmental and socio-economic impacts (+/-) of large-scale, blue water MPAs (and under what conditions those impacts are likely to be realized). Additionally, as new technologies and innovations are developed that allow for monitoring and impact

evaluation at scale, setting an agreed upon research agenda can help direct finite resources toward the highest priority knowledge gaps to assess conservation impact of blue water MPAs.

Biodiversity

Key themes addressed here include: (1) protection of intact open ocean (pelagic) ecosystems; (2) conservation of dynamic ecosystems and highly migratory species; and (3) climate change mitigation and adaptation.

- **Protection of intact open ocean (pelagic) ecosystems:** Large blue water MPAs offer the ability to protect whole ecosystems and interdependent habitats from multiple stressors, including open-ocean and deep-sea habitats as well as important pelagic features (Toonen et al. 2013; Wilhelm et al. 2014). Benefits of this approach include protecting vulnerable, under-valued, and bycatch species and helping to maintain trophic linkages (Travis et al. 2014). Recent research has highlighted the importance of integrated species and habitat protection in open ocean ecosystems, challenging vertically stratified management (e.g., MPAs protecting the seabed while the water column remains open to fishing) and single species approaches. For example, O’Leary and Roberts (2017; 2018) cite evidence of linkages through the water column, and between the water column and seabed (e.g., energy production and transfer in food webs, cycling of nutrients and raw materials, shifts in habitat use, and daily and seasonal vertical migrations associated with megafauna and mesopelagic fish), and argue that mobile marine organisms provide structure-forming biomass, constituting “habitat” in the open ocean. That said, the state of knowledge on the strength and nature of these ecological and environmental linkages is sparse, which limits effective selection and design of MPAs. Critical gaps include spatial scale, the influence of food-web cascades in open water ecosystems on seabed and water column ecosystems, and effects of pelagic fishing on ecosystem functioning and provision of services in offshore environments (O’Leary and Roberts 2018). Approaches that have been taken to develop protected areas in related date-limited ecosystems, such as the deep sea, may be useful to address similar challenges for pelagic ecosystem MPA design and implementation (Wedding et al. 2013; 2015).
- **Conservation of dynamic ecosystems and highly migratory species:** The dynamism of the open ocean, where ecosystems shift substantially within and across years and species often move hundreds of kilometers, poses a challenge to conventional notions of how protected areas function (Kaplan et al. 2014; Young et al. 2015). Despite this dynamism, there are important pelagic features (e.g., upwelling cells, thermal fronts, eddies) that are predictable in space and time (Alpine and Hobday 2007). However, the complexities of pelagic systems are not well understood, which can make informed decisions on MPA placement a challenge (Game et al. 2009). For pelagic species conservation, MPAs in open ocean environments are most likely to provide greater benefits to less mobile species (e.g., small ocean pelagics, and large and small nearshore pelagics) (Davies et al. 2012). Highly mobile species present more of a challenge, and modeling studies suggest that MPAs for these species should be very large or be part of a network that covers a significant portion of the species’ range (Moffitt et al. 2009; Davies et al. 2012). Alternately, they could cover smaller, demographically critical target areas such as nursery, spawning, and foraging areas or migratory routes (Game et al. 2010). Challenges arise for species that do not exhibit site fidelity, or clear spawning or feeding migrations (Kaplan et al. 2010), though Game et al. (2009) suggest that this could be combatted through temporally variable MPAs.

In terms of empirical evidence, the benefits of blue water MPAs for highly mobile species with large ranges – such as marine mammals, turtles, sharks, tunas, and other pelagic fish – has not yet been

comprehensively assessed (Hyrenback et al. 2000; Davies et al. 2017; White et al. 2017). However, there is increasing evidence that mobile species can benefit from spatial protection (Edgar et al. 2014). For example, Jensen et al. (2010) showed significant and rapid increases in striped marlin abundance during two separate multi-year closures of the Mexican EEZ to longline fishing; Young et al. (2015) demonstrated the effectiveness of a network of pelagic MPAs in the Pacific for three species of seabirds; Pala (2013) highlighted that some Chagos tuna spend their entire lives within the MPA; and White et al. (2017) found that LMPAs provide substantial, though incomplete, protection for grey reef sharks. Finally, it's important to recognize that because of the extensive movements of migratory species, many studies point to the need for strong complementary measures outside of MPA boundaries, such as dynamic ocean management (DOM),² fisheries management, and precautionary regulation of emerging industrial activities (Maxwell et al. 2015; O'Leary and Roberts 2018; Sibert et al. 2012). Issues related to blue water MPAs and fisheries management are addressed in more detail in the Fisheries section.

- **Climate change mitigation and adaptation:** Some have argued that large-scale, blue water MPAs are ineffective at protecting ecosystems from global stressors such as climate change and ocean acidification (e.g., Hilborn 2017). Others hypothesize that blue water MPAs may play a role in climate adaptation and mitigation. For example, by providing “stepping stones” and “landing zones” for climate migrants; potentially buffering acidification through protection of open ocean mesopelagic fish via excretion of gut carbonates; preventing release of carbon from sediments disturbed by fishing gear; increasing resilience in the face of cumulative impacts through (1) protection of larger, more resilient populations with greater reproductive outputs, (2) reduction of other human stressors, (3) promotion of genetic diversity that provides the raw material for adaptation, and (4) protection of apex predators that confer increased ecosystem stability (Roberts et al. 2017; Wilhelm et al. 2014). Relatively unexplored areas include the role of fish in nutrient cycling, which is critical for primary productivity.

Fisheries

Key themes related to fisheries outcomes of blue water MPAs include: (1) spillover; (2) effort reduction; (3) management of highly migratory fish stocks; and (4) managing multiple tuna stocks.

- **Spillover:** Blue water MPAs may increase the recruitment of eggs and larvae into adjacent fishing grounds. They also provide opportunities to “fish the line,” where fishers can focus their fishing efforts on the boundary line of an MPA where individuals from fish stocks spill over the MPA border into adjacent fishing grounds (Di Lorenzo et al. 2016). For example, Boerder et al. (2017) found that there is evidence of fishing the line on the western boundary of the Galapagos Marine Reserve, providing stabilized catch and increased stock availability for fishers in the area. However, the larger an MPA becomes, the smaller the edge to area ratio, which, depending on the mobility of the species, may lead to less spillover (Singleton and Roberts 2014). Furthermore, under some conditions, anthropogenic impacts outside of MPAs may outpace reproduction and recruitment inside, which could result in population declines (Moffitt et al. 2009; White et al. 2017). Modelling

² DOM recognizes the non-stationarity of ocean environments and is defined as management that rapidly changes in space and time in response to changes in the ocean and its users through the integration of near real-time biological, oceanographic, social and/or economic data (Maxwell et al. 2015). DOM can provide a balance between ocean resource use and conservation and meet multiple objectives—for example, managing target quotas, bycatch reduction, and reducing interactions with species of conservation concern.

results suggest that excessive spillover can rapidly reduce or eliminate MPA benefits, especially if combined with effort displacement (Davies et al. 2012).

- **Effort reduction:** Blue water MPAs can serve as a management tool aimed at reducing fishing pressures (e.g., effort reduction was an aim of the ICCAT time/area closure in the eastern tropical Atlantic) (Torres-Irineo et al. 2011). However, a common criticism of MPAs is that rather than reducing fishing effort, they only displace it to other areas (Hilborn 2018; Greenstreet et al. 2009; Kaplan et al. 2010). Rebuttals include arguments that some mobile species, even highly migratory tuna or billfish, may stay within the boundaries of suitably-sized protected areas (Silbert and Hampton 2003; Wilhelm et al. 2014; Friedlander et al. 2017). This topic represents a significant knowledge gap, as there has been no major, systematic analyses of whether MPAs increase fish abundance throughout a larger region (considering impacts both inside and outside of reserves), and under what circumstances (Hilborn 2018).
- **Management of highly migratory fish stocks:** Blue water MPAs may conserve stocks that spawn, migrate, and forage fully or in part in the protected zone. Productive ocean features such as seamounts, near-island hotspots, and upwelling zones have been shown to act as natural aggregating sites for highly migratory species such as tuna and skipjack (Morato et al. 2008; Richardson et al. 2018; Gove et al. 2016). Yellowfin tuna have been found to utilize habitat differently depending on age and habitat productivity (Schaefer et al. 2011), and Atlantic Bluefin tuna have been found to have site fidelity to spawning and foraging grounds (Block et al. 2005). Having areas where schools are not disturbed by fishing activities or other impacts such as shipping may help protect species during vulnerable life stages. Protection of key spawning grounds has been proposed as a viable conservation strategy for tuna (WWF 2016), and more research is needed on the viability of this approach as well as the identification of spawning sites and other key areas used during different critical life-history stages for targeted pelagic species. On the other hand, some argue that blue water MPAs may be unnecessary because fisheries management can achieve similar management outcomes (e.g., reduce fishing effort and rebuild overexploited stocks, reduce broader ecosystem impacts via bycatch mitigation and seasonal closures) (Hilborn 2016; Costello et al. 2016; Graham et al. 2007). Uncertainty and data limitations also factor into this debate. For example, a weakness of blue water MPAs for tuna stocks, compared to the use of effort and catch limits, is that estimates of the area that would need to be closed to fishing to achieve the target reference point for spawning biomass are likely to be uncertain or have substantial errors due to model assumptions and lack of uniform distribution of individuals within the stock. In contrast, harvest strategies based on catch limits and reference points may be a more reliable way of maintaining the desired spawning biomass (Silbert et al. 2012). However, a counterpoint that may be worth discussing is whether blue water MPAs may be used in fisheries management because they are perceived as conceptually far simpler as a management effort compared with many fisheries regulations. Though, questions remain about the ease of enforcement.

With regards to a research agenda, the potential effectiveness of large, blue water MPAs as a fisheries management tool for tuna and other highly migratory species will require filling gaps in our understanding of the number and distribution of self-replenishing stocks, and the typical movement patterns of individual fish within each stock, and further identification of habitat usage during different life-history stages (e.g., spawning sites). Three foundational research needs may include:

1. Genetic analyses of population structure to identify the number and distributions of stocks comprising each species.

2. Once each stock has been delineated, the size (total biomass) of each stock and annual sustainable catches from each stock.
 3. Typical movement patterns of individual fish within each stock.
- **Managing multiple tuna stocks:** Assuming there are multiple stocks for each species of tuna, any decision to completely protect one or more stocks with MPAs may have more disadvantages than advantages. By definition, a tuna stock does not replenish a neighbouring stock effectively, so protecting an entire stock would not help sustain catches of tuna across a broader area. Any application of blue water MPAs would need to be done specifically for each self-replenishing stock of each tuna species. Given that the spatial stock structures of yellowfin and bigeye tuna are unlikely to be the same (Grewe et al. 2015, Richardson et al. 2018), it is improbable that blue water MPAs dedicated to help manage a yellowfin tuna would have advantages for management of a bigeye tuna. Consequently, there would need to be a series of blue water MPAs for yellowfin and another set for bigeye. This would add up to a complicated set of management arrangements compared to applying catch limits to each stock of each species. When other highly migratory species such as skipjack tuna and South Pacific albacore are added to the mix, the situation becomes even more complex.

Human Dimensions

Human dimensions (HD) are defined as the “the cultural, social, economic, political, and institutional factors that affect and are affected by large-scale marine conservation efforts” (Gray et al. 2017). The human dimensions of blue water MPAs are generally poorly understood – in part due to the relatively recent establishment of most of these MPAs. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in sustained and systematic consideration of human dimensions of large-scale MPAs (LMPAs), which can help to inform establishment, design and management. Much of this momentum has grown from Big Ocean’s 2016 “Think Tank” on Human Dimensions of LMPAs, which identified priority topics for future research including scoping human dimensions, governance, politics, social and economic outcomes, and culture and tradition (Gray et al. 2017; Christie et al. 2017) (Appendix I).

This section focuses primarily on social outcomes, which include both “social change processes” and “social impacts,” and encompass a range of dimensions (e.g., cultural, demographic, economic, health, institutional, political) (Vanclay 2002). Due to factors such as their sheer size, remoteness, and complex socioeconomic and political contexts, blue water and LMPAs can produce distinctive social outcomes that warrant research attention (Gruby et al. 2017). While outcomes of conventional MPAs are usually experienced at a small-scale by nearby resource users, blue water and LMPAs tend to intersect with national and international politics and policy processes, therefore also producing outcomes at higher levels of social organization (i.e., jurisdiction-wide, regional agreements) (Gruby et al. 2017).

- **Sociocultural outcomes:** A well-documented concern with blue water MPAs is that their designation and management can undermine social justice or lead to disempowerment or displacement of stakeholders, especially when implemented through top-down processes. This theme is consistent with the literature and practical knowledge base from terrestrial efforts. For blue water MPAs, there have been concerns over political motivation (e.g., Chagos Marine Reserve, De Santo et al. 2011), inadequate stakeholder consultation, and “ocean grabbing” by central management authorities (Bennett et al. 2015; Christie et al. 2017; De Santo et al. 2013; O’Leary et al 2018). These issues can be especially difficult for blue water MPAs, since these sites can pose major challenges to sustained, comprehensive engagement with an often more remote and diverse constituency (Kittinger et al.

2011; Wilhelm et al. 2014; Davies et al. 2018). On the other hand, blue water MPAs can lead to positive outcomes and have played a role in protecting cultural values and heritage (Wilhelm et al. 2014; Gaymer et al., 2014). For example, Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument, the world's first marine UNESCO world heritage site that is designated for both biological and cultural significance, successfully reflects Native Hawaiian values and practices (Kikiloi et al. 2017). In addition, the Phoenix Island Protected Area (PIPA) – despite its remote location – has led to perceptions of strengthened national pride and reinforcement of aspects of I-Kiribati culture (Gruby et al. 2017). Blue water LMPAs have also played a role in validating indigenous rights in Rapa Nui and the CNMI, where blue water MPA processes have given local and indigenous leaders political leverage to advance territorial claims at unprecedented, jurisdiction-wide scales (Gruby et al. 2017).

- **Economic outcomes:** Many of the socioeconomic concerns around blue water MPAs focus on the potential for lost economic benefits, particularly for the fishing and mining sectors, which may make up a substantial portion of the economy of some countries (Wilhelm et al. 2014; Richmond et al. 2015). The potential displacement of small-scale fishers as well as local and indigenous communities – including implications for seafood supplies, livelihoods, and food security – is another important consideration (Friedlander et al. 2016). Counterarguments suggest that in general, blue water MPAs have been placed in areas with fewer commercial interests, which, when combined with participatory design that permits artisanal fishing, can help address these concerns (Devillers et al; O’Leary et al. 2018). In some cases, conservation financing mechanisms have helped to secure economic outcomes from blue water MPAs. For example, in Kiribati, a conservation trust fund (PIPA Trust) was established that obligated partners (including international funders and NGOs) to compensate the government for lost tuna revenue. In terms of positive impacts, some argue that blue water MPAs can play a role in mitigating global economic inequity related to fisheries. For example, Palau is using its National Marine Sanctuary to “reclaim its EEZ” via processes that are directed toward crowding out foreign tuna fishing and developing a domestic fleet that could feed both visitors and residents (Wabnitz et al. 2018). However, important questions remain around whether and how this fleet will expand and what this will mean for fish prices, fishing pressure, and reef conservation, and how this will intersect with the PNA and other fishing agreements (Gruby et al. 2017). This example is illustrative of uncertainty and lack of empirical data around the purported economic benefits that blue water MPAs can deliver domestically and internationally to help mitigate potential losses (e.g., fisheries revenue).

With regards to equity, other arguments suggest blue water MPAs could help to reduce inequality in the distribution of fisheries benefits on the high seas – where 10 countries capture 71% of landed value (Sumaila et al. 2015, Cheung et al. 2017) – by leading to more benefits accrued through fishing in EEZs. Finally, from a broader perspective, benefits arising from protection can be accrued globally, including ecosystem services such as climate and biodiversity refugia (O’Leary et al. 2018). With respect to research needs, rigorous economic analyses of blue water MPAs represent a significant gap in the literature. Gray et al. (2017) identified several important areas for future work including: economic trade-offs, funding dynamics (e.g., do LMPAs divert funding away from nearshore activities, especially those that support local food security?), and understanding the true costs of establishment and long-term management (e.g., to what degree are there economies of scale (Balmford et al. 2004), and do these offset management, surveillance, and enforcement costs?).

Design, Governance, and Management Considerations

Finally, there is a growing body of literature on conditions that influence the impacts of blue water MPAs. Here, we highlight themes in the literature focused on placement and governance challenges and enabling conditions and best practices.

- **Placement and governance challenges:** A common criticism is that conservation outcomes of blue water LMPAs are often limited by their placement, which some argue is based more on political expediency (i.e., remote, “residual” areas with minimal threats and human use, and thus relatively low conservation potential), resulting in MPAs that are not necessarily science-based, nor fully ecologically representative or well-connected at a global scale (Devillers et al. 2015). Counterarguments focus on the value of precautionary approaches and proactive ocean protection (O’Leary et al. 2018), as well as the utility of using comparatively pristine ecosystems as modern-day baselines (Big Ocean 2013). There is also new evidence that globally, cumulative impacts are significantly higher in LMPAs than outside, refuting the critique that they only occur in pristine areas (Davies et al. 2017). Finally, challenges around effective placement are compounded by the fact that progress towards an ecologically representative global network is constrained because most of the pelagic ocean (64%) – where several migratory fish stocks are likely to be found – falls in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ). Policy and regulatory mechanisms for creating MPAs in ABNJ are limited and effective governance remains a major challenge (Davies et al. 2012; Cullis-Suzuki & Pauly 2010; Game et al. 2009).
- **Enabling conditions and best practices:** A final theme in the social science literature worth highlighting is the nascent focus on factors that contribute to social and ecological outcomes of blue water MPAs. For example, some of the factors related to success include: integration of culture and traditions, effective public and stakeholder engagement, maintenance of livelihoods and wellbeing, promotion of economic sustainability, conflict management and resolution, transparency and matching institutions and ideas, compliance and enforcement, legitimate and appropriate governance, and social justice and empowerment (Kittinger et al. 2011; Ban et al. 2017; Day et al. 2017; Christie et al 2017). Moving forward, there is a need for more rigorous empirical investigation of the social, ecological, and governance mechanisms that contribute to outcomes (Ban et al. 2017).

Other relevant research agendas

Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities Identified by the Big Ocean Think Tank's Community of Practice (Christie et al. 2017)

- **Governance:** (1) What is the level of community/public engagement and empowerment at new/established LSMPAs? (2) What is the influence of differing LSMPA governance frameworks on public/stakeholder engagement and perception of LSMPAs? (3) What is the relative effectiveness of different LSMPA governance approaches?
- **Politics:** (1) What are the motives and agendas of NGO partners and stakeholders in supporting LSMPA designation and management?
- **Socio-Economic:** (1) How can a wide range of human uses and interests (economic, cultural, etc.) be best incorporated within LSMPA design and management planning? (2) What are the ecosystem services of LSMPAs and who are the beneficiaries and cost-bearers? What are the relative costs and benefits of LSMPAs compared to other marine management tools? (3) What is the perceived level of impact (positive and/or negative) of LSMPAs on stakeholders, including stakeholder connection to the site? (4) What is the socioeconomic value of living and cultural resources within LSMPAs? How can LSMPAs be classified in relation to different HD aspects and issues?
- **Culture and Tradition:** (1) How can cultural practices/values and traditional knowledge be best incorporated into LSMPA design and management? (2) What is the level of equity in values, particularly cultural and intrinsic values? What is the level of understanding of stakeholder values?

A Shared Research Agenda for Large-scale Marine Protected Areas (Big Ocean 2013)

- **Biological and ecological characterization:** Understand, quantify and compare the individual and collective contributions of Big Ocean sites to the total biological and ecological diversity of the globe.
- **Connectivity:** Understand the linkages of Big Ocean sites within their own site, amongst sites, as well as to other regions. In this context, connectivity does not solely refer to the biological connectivity through the movement of organisms and their larvae, but also encompasses physical connectivity through the circulation of winds and currents, as well as anthropogenic connectivity through the spread of man-made impacts.
- **Monitoring of temporal trends:** characterize historical baselines and understand temporal trajectories of ecosystems, so that resource population levels can be fore and hind casted at various times.

References

- Alpine, J.E., Hobday, A.J., 2007. Area requirements and pelagic protected areas: is size an impediment to implementation? *Marine and Freshwater Research* 58, 558. <https://doi.org/10.1071/MF06214>
- Balmford, A., Gravestock, P., Hockley, N., McClean, C.J., Roberts, C.M., 2004. The worldwide costs of marine protected areas. *PNAS* 101, 9694–9697. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0403239101>
- Ban, N.C., Davies, T.E., Aguilera, S.E., Brooks, C., Cox, M., Epstein, G., Evans, L., Maxwell, S.M., Nenadovich, M., 2017. Social and ecological effectiveness of large marine protected areas. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.01.003>
- Bennett, N.J., Govan, H., Satterfield, T., 2015. Ocean grabbing. *Marine Policy* 57, 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.03.026>
- Big Ocean Planning Team. 2013. Big Ocean: A shared research agenda for large-scale marine protected areas. Big Ocean planning team in collaboration with the Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument & UNESCO World Heritage Site (PMNM), NOAA Office of National Marine Sanctuaries.
- Block, B.A., Teo, S.L.H., Walli, A., Boustany, A., Stokesbury, M.J.W., Farwell, C.J., Weng, K.C., Dewar, H., Williams, T.D., 2005. Electronic tagging and population structure of Atlantic bluefin tuna. *Nature* 434, 1121–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature03463>
- Boerder, K., Bryndum-Buchholz, A., Worm, B., 2017. Interactions of tuna fisheries with the Galápagos marine reserve. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 585, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12399>
- Buckworth, R.C., Newman, S.J., Ovenden, J.R., Lester, R.J.G., McPherson, G.R., n.d. The Stock Structure of Northern and Western Australian Spanish Mackerel 232.
- Cheung, W.W.L., Jones, M.C., Lam, V.W.Y., Miller, D.D., Ota, Y., Teh, L., Sumaila, U.R., 2017. Transform high seas management to build climate resilience in marine seafood supply. *Fish and Fisheries* 18, 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12177>
- Costello, C., Ovando, D., Clavelle, T., Strauss, C.K., Hilborn, R., Melnychuk, M.C., Branch, T.A., Gaines, S.D., Szuwalski, C.S., Cabral, R.B., Rader, D.N., Leland, A., 2016. Global fishery prospects under contrasting management regimes. *PNAS* 201520420. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1520420113>
- Cullis-suzuki, S., Pauly, D., 2010. Marine Protected Area Costs as “Beneficial” Fisheries Subsidies: A Global Evaluation. *Coastal Management* 113.
- Davies, T.E., Epstein, G., Aguilera, S.E., Brooks, C.M., Cox, M., Evans, L.S., Maxwell, S.M., Nenadovic, M., Ban, N.C., 2018. Assessing trade-offs in large marine protected areas. *PLOS ONE* 13, e0195760. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195760>
- Davies, T.E., Maxwell, S.M., Kaschner, K., Garilao, C., Ban, N.C., 2017. Large marine protected areas represent biodiversity now and under climate change. *Scientific Reports* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-08758-5>

- Davies, T.K., Martin, S., Mees, C., Chassot, E., Kaplan, D.M., 2012. A review of the conservation benefits of marine protected areas for pelagic species associated with fisheries 37.
- Day, J.C., 2017. Effective Public Participation is Fundamental for Marine Conservation—Lessons from a Large-Scale MPA. *Coastal Management* 45, 470–486.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2017.1373452>
- De Santo, E.M., 2013. Missing marine protected area (MPA) targets: How the push for quantity over quality undermines sustainability and social justice. *Journal of Environmental Management* 124, 137–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.01.033>
- De Santo, E.M., Jones, P.J.S., Miller, A.M.M., 2011. Fortress conservation at sea: A commentary on the Chagos marine protected area. *Marine Policy* 35, 258–260.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2010.09.004>
- Devillers, R., Pressey, R.L., Grech, A., Kittinger, J.N., Edgar, G.J., Ward, T., Watson, R., 2015. Reinventing residual reserves in the sea: are we favouring ease of establishment over need for protection? *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 25, 480–504.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2445>
- Di Lorenzo, M., Claudet, J., Guidetti, P., 2016. Spillover from marine protected areas to adjacent fisheries has an ecological and a fishery component. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 32, 62–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2016.04.004>
- Edgar, G.J., Stuart-Smith, R.D., Willis, T.J., Kininmonth, S., Baker, S.C., Banks, S., Barrett, N.S., Becerro, M.A., Bernard, A.T.F., Berkhout, J., Buxton, C.D., Campbell, S.J., Cooper, A.T., Davey, M., Edgar, S.C., Försterra, G., Galván, D.E., Irigoyen, A.J., Kushner, D.J., Moura, R., Parnell, P.E., Shears, N.T., Soler, G., Strain, E.M.A., Thomson, R.J., 2014. Global conservation outcomes depend on marine protected areas with five key features. *Nature* 506, 216–220.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13022>
- FAO Workshop on Impacts of Marine Protected Areas on Fisheries Yield, F.C. and E., Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2016. Report of the FAO Workshop on Impacts of Marine Protected Areas on Fisheries Yield, Fishing Communities and Ecosystems: Rome, Italy, 16-18 June 2015.
- Friedlander, A.M., Wagner, D., Gaymer, C.F., Wilhelm, T., 'Aulani, Lewis, N., Brooke, S., Kikiloi, K., Varmer, O., 2016. Co-operation between large-scale MPAs: successful experiences from the Pacific Ocean: Cooperation Between Pacific Large-Scale MPAs. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 126–141. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2645>
- Friedlander, A. M., A. Filous, and Y. Golbuu. 2017. Preliminary results on the examination of tuna and marlin movement in Palau's National Marine Sanctuary using satellite tags. Fisheries Ecology Research Lab, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Pristine Seas, National Geographic Society; and Palau International Coral Reef Center.

- Game, E.T., Grantham, H.S., Hobday, A.J., Pressey, R.L., Lombard, A.T., Beckley, L.E., Gjerde, K., Bustamante, R., Possingham, H.P., Richardson, A.J., 2009. Pelagic protected areas: the missing dimension in ocean conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 24, 360–369.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.01.011>
- Gaymer, C.F., Stadel, A.V., Ban, N.C., Cárcamo, P.F., Ierna, J., Lieberknecht, L.M., 2014. Merging top-down and bottom-up approaches in marine protected areas planning: experiences from around the globe: MERGING TOP-DOWN AND BOTTOM-UP APPROACHES IN MPAs. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 24, 128–144. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2508>
- Gove, J.M., McManus, M.A., Neuheimer, A.B., Polovina, J.J., Drazen, J.C., Smith, C.R., Merrifield, M.A., Friedlander, A.M., Ehses, J.S., Young, C.W., Dillon, A.K., Williams, G.J., 2016. Near-island biological hotspots in barren ocean basins. *Nature Communications* 7, 10581.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10581>
- Graham, N., Ferro, R.S.T., Karp, W.A., MacMullen, P., 2007. Fishing practice, gear design, and the ecosystem approach—three case studies demonstrating the effect of management strategy on gear selectivity and discards. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 64, 744–750.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsm059>
- Graham, N.A.J., McClanahan, T.R., 2013. The Last Call for Marine Wilderness? *BioScience* 63, 397–402.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2013.63.5.13>
- Gray, N.J., Bennett, N.J., Day, J.C., Gruby, R.L., Wilhelm, T., 'Aulani, Christie, P., 2017. Human Dimensions of Large-scale Marine Protected Areas: Advancing Research and Practice. *Coastal Management* 0, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2017.1373448>
- Greenstreet, S.P.R., Fraser, H.M., Piet, G.J., 2008. Using MPAs to address regional-scale ecological objectives in the North Sea: modelling the effects of fishing effort displacement. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 66, 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn214>
- Grewe, P.M., Feutry, P., Hill, P.L., Gunasekera, R.M., Schaefer, K.M., Itano, D.G., Fuller, D.W., Foster, S.D., Davies, C.R., 2015. Evidence of discrete yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*) populations demands rethink of management for this globally important resource. *Scientific Reports* 5.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16916>
- Gruby, R.L., Fairbanks, L., Acton, L., Artis, E., Campbell, L.M., Gray, N.J., Mitchell, L., Zigler, S.B.J., Wilson, K., 2017. Conceptualizing Social Outcomes of Large Marine Protected Areas. *Coastal Management* 45, 416–435. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2017.1373449>
- Gruby, R.L., Gray, N.J., Campbell, L.M., Acton, L., 2016. Toward a Social Science Research Agenda for Large Marine Protected Areas: Social science and large MPAs. *Conservation Letters* 9, 153–163.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12194>
- Hilborn, R., 2018. Are MPAs effective? *ICES J Mar Sci* 75, 1160–1162.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsx068>

- Hilborn, R., 2016. Policy: Marine biodiversity needs more than protection. *Nature News* 535, 224. <https://doi.org/10.1038/535224a>
- Hyrenbach, K.D., Forney, K.A., Dayton, P.K., 2000. Marine protected areas and ocean basin management 22.
- Jensen, O.P., Ortega-Garcia, S., Martell, S.J.D., Ahrens, R.N.M., Domeier, M.L., Walters, C.J., Kitchell, J.F., 2010. Local management of a “highly migratory species”: The effects of long-line closures and recreational catch-and-release for Baja California striped marlin fisheries. *Progress in Oceanography* 86, 176–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2010.04.020>
- Kaplan, D.M., Chassot, E., Amandé, J.M., Dueri, S., Demarcq, H., Dagorn, L., Fonteneau, A., 2014. Spatial management of Indian Ocean tropical tuna fisheries: potential and perspectives. *ICES J Mar Sci* 71, 1728–1749. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fst233>
- Kaplan, D.M., Chassot, E., Gruss, A., Fonteneau, A., 2010. Pelagic MPAs: The devil is in the details. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 25, 62–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.09.003>
- Kikiloi, K., Friedlander, A.M., Wilhelm, 'Aulani, Lewis, N., Quiocho, K., Jr, W. 'Āila, Kaho'ohalahala, S., 2017. Papahānaumokuākea: Integrating Culture in the Design and Management of one of the World's Largest Marine Protected Areas. *Coastal Management* 0, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2017.1373450>
- Kittinger, J.N., Dowling, A., Purves, A.R., Milne, N.A., Olsson, P., 2011. Marine Protected Areas, Multiple-Agency Management, and Monumental Surprise in the Northwestern Hawaiian Islands. *Journal of Marine Biology* 2011, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/241374>
- Koldewey, H.J., Curnick, D., Harding, S., Harrison, L.R., Gollock, M., 2010. Potential benefits to fisheries and biodiversity of the Chagos Archipelago/British Indian Ocean Territory as a no-take marine reserve. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 60, 1906–1915. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2010.10.002>
- Lehodey, P., Senina, I., Calmettes, B., Hampton, J., Nicol, S., 2013. Modelling the impact of climate change on Pacific skipjack tuna population and fisheries. *Climatic Change* 119, 95–109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-012-0595-1>
- Lehodey, P., Senina, I., Murtugudde, R., 2008. A spatial ecosystem and populations dynamics model (SEAPODYM) – Modeling of tuna and tuna-like populations. *Progress in Oceanography* 78, 304–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2008.06.004>
- Levin, L.A., Baco, A.R., Bowden, D.A., Colaco, A., Cordes, E.E., Cunha, M.R., Demopoulos, A.W.J., Gobin, J., Grupe, B.M., Le, J., Metaxas, A., Netburn, A.N., Rouse, G.W., Thurber, A.R., Tunnicliffe, V., Van Dover, C.L., Vanreusel, A., Watling, L., 2016. Hydrothermal Vents and Methane Seeps: Rethinking the Sphere of Influence. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00072>

- Maxwell, S.M., Hazen, E.L., Lewison, R.L., Dunn, D.C., Bailey, H., Bograd, S.J., Briscoe, D.K., Fossette, S., Hobday, A.J., Bennett, M., Benson, S., Caldwell, M.R., Costa, D.P., Dewar, H., Eguchi, T., Hazen, L., Kohin, S., Sippel, T., Crowder, L.B., 2015. Dynamic ocean management: Defining and conceptualizing real-time management of the ocean. *Marine Policy* 58, 42–50.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.03.014>
- Moffitt, E.A., Botsford, L.W., Kaplan, D.M., O'Farrell, M.R., 2009. Marine reserve networks for species that move within a home range. *Ecological Applications* 19, 1835–1847.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1101.1>
- Morato, T., Varkey, D., Damaso, C., Machete, M., Santos, M., Prieto, R., Pitcher, T., Santos, R., 2008. Evidence of a seamount effect on aggregating visitors. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 357, 23–32.
<https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07269>
- O'Leary, B.C., Ban, N.C., Fernandez, M., Friedlander, A.M., García-Borboroglu, P., Golbuu, Y., Guidetti, P., Harris, J.M., Hawkins, J.P., Langlois, T., McCauley, D.J., Pikitch, E.K., Richmond, R.H., Roberts, C.M., 2018. Addressing Criticisms of Large-Scale Marine Protected Areas. *BioScience* 68, 359–370.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biy021>
- O'Leary, B.C., Roberts, C.M., 2018. Ecological connectivity across ocean depths: Implications for protected area design. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 15, e00431.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2018.e00431>
- O'Leary, B.C., Roberts, C.M., 2017. The Structuring Role of Marine Life in Open Ocean Habitat: Importance to International Policy. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 4.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00268>
- Pala, C., 2013a. The True Challenge of Giant Marine Reserves--Response. *Science* 340, 811–811.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.340.6134.811-a>
- Pala, C., 2013b. The True Challenge of Giant Marine Reserves--Response. *Science* 340, 811–811.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.340.6134.811-a>
- Richardson, A.J., Downes, K.J., Nolan, E.T., Brickle, P., Brown, J., Weber, N., Weber, S.B., 2018. Residency and reproductive status of yellowfin tuna in a proposed large-scale pelagic marine protected area. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 28, 1308–1316.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2936>
- Roberts, C.M., O'Leary, B.C., McCauley, D.J., Cury, P.M., Duarte, C.M., Lubchenco, J., Pauly, D., Sáenz-Arroyo, A., Sumaila, U.R., Wilson, R.W., Worm, B., Castilla, J.C., 2017. Marine reserves can mitigate and promote adaptation to climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 114, 6167–6175. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1701262114>
- Saunders, T., Mayfield, S., Hogg, A., 2008. Using a simple morphometric marker to identify spatial units for abalone fishery management. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 66, 305–314.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn212>

- Schaefer, K., Fuller, D., Hampton, J., Caillot, S., Leroy, B., Itano, D., 2015. Movements, dispersion, and mixing of bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*) tagged and released in the equatorial Central Pacific Ocean, with conventional and archival tags. *Fisheries Research* 161, 336–355.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2014.08.018>
- Schaefer, K.M., Fuller, D.W., Block, B.A., 2011. Movements, behavior, and habitat utilization of yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*) in the Pacific Ocean off Baja California, Mexico, determined from archival tag data analyses, including unscented Kalman filtering. *Fisheries Research* 112, 22–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2011.08.006>
- Scott, K.N., 2012. Conservation on the High Seas: Developing the Concept of the High Seas Marine Protected Areas. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law* 27, 849–857.
<https://doi.org/10.1163/15718085-12341243>
- Senina, I., P. Lehodey, N. Smith, and J. Hampton. 2018. Impact of climate change on tropical tuna species and tuna fisheries in Pacific Island waters and high seas areas. Pacific Community (SPC) and Collecte Localisation Satellites (CLS).
- Sibert, J., Senina, I., Lehodey, P., Hampton, J., 2012a. Shifting from marine reserves to maritime zoning for conservation of Pacific bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109, 18221–18225. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1209468109>
- Sibert, J., Senina, I., Lehodey, P., Hampton, J., 2012b. Shifting from marine reserves to maritime zoning for conservation of Pacific bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109, 18221–18225. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1209468109>
- Singleton, R.L., Roberts, C.M., 2014. The contribution of very large marine protected areas to marine conservation: Giant leaps or smoke and mirrors? *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 87, 7–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.07.067>
- SPC. 2018. Current knowledge, key uncertainties and future research directions for defining the stock structure of skipjack, yellowfin, bigeye and South Pacific albacore tunas in the Pacific Ocean. SPC (Pacific Community), Developed for Conservation International (CI) as part of the GEF-funded, World Bank implemented Ocean Partnerships for sustainable fisheries and biodiversity conservation (OPP), a sub-project of the Common Oceans ABNJ Program led by UN-FAO.
- Stefansson, G., Rosenberg, A.A., 2005. Combining control measures for more effective management of fisheries under uncertainty: quotas, effort limitation and protected areas. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 360, 133–146.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2004.1579>
- Sumaila, U., Zeller, D., Watson, R., Alder, J., Pauly, D., 2007. Potential costs and benefits of marine reserves in the high seas. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 345, 305–310.
<https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07065>

- Sumaila, U.R., Cheung, W.W.L., Lam, V.W.Y., Pauly, D., Herrick, S., 2011. Climate change impacts on the biophysics and economics of world fisheries. *Nature Climate Change* 1, 449–456. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1301>
- Toonen, R.J., Wilhelm, T. 'Aulani, Maxwell, S.M., Wagner, D., Bowen, B.W., Sheppard, C.R.C., Taei, S.M., Teroroko, T., Moffitt, R., Gaymer, C.F., Morgan, L., Lewis, N., Sheppard, A.L.S., Parks, J., Friedlander, A.M., 2013. One size does not fit all: The emerging frontier in large-scale marine conservation. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 77, 7–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2013.10.039>
- Torres-Irineo, E., Gaertner, D., de Molina, A.D., Ariz, J., 2011. Effects of time-area closure on tropical tuna purse-seine fleet dynamics through some fishery indicators. *Aquatic Living Resources* 24, 337–350. <https://doi.org/10.1051/alr/2011143>
- Travis, J., Coleman, F.C., Auster, P.J., Cury, P.M., Estes, J.A., Orensanz, J., Peterson, C.H., Power, M.E., Steneck, R.S., Wootton, J.T., 2014. Integrating the invisible fabric of nature into fisheries management. *PNAS* 111, 581–584. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1305853111>
- Vanclay, F., 2002. Conceptualising social impacts. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 22, 183–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0195-9255\(01\)00105-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0195-9255(01)00105-6)
- Wabnitz, C.C.C., Cisneros-Montemayor, A.M., Hanich, Q., Ota, Y., 2018. Ecotourism, climate change and reef fish consumption in Palau: Benefits, trade-offs and adaptation strategies. *Marine Policy* 88, 323–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.07.022>
- Wedding, L., Maxwell, S., Hyrenbach, D., Dunn, D., Roberts, J., Briscoe, D., Hines, E., Halpin, P., 2016. Geospatial approaches to support pelagic conservation planning and adaptive management. *Endangered Species Research* 30, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3354/esr00716>
- Wedding, L.M., Friedlander, A.M., Kittinger, J.N., Watling, L., Gaines, S.D., Bennett, M., Hardy, S.M., Smith, C.R., 2013. From principles to practice: a spatial approach to systematic conservation planning in the deep sea. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 280, 20131684–20131684. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.1684>
- Wedding, L.M., Reiter, S.M., Smith, C.R., Gjerde, K.M., Kittinger, J.N., Friedlander, A.M., Gaines, S.D., Clark, M.R., Thurnherr, A.M., Hardy, S.M., Crowder, L.B., 2015. Managing mining of the deep seabed. *Science* 349, 144–145. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac6647>
- West, C.D., Dytham, C., Righton, D., Pitchford, J.W., 2009. Preventing overexploitation of migratory fish stocks: the efficacy of marine protected areas in a stochastic environment. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 66, 1919–1930. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsp159>
- White, T.D., Carlisle, A.B., Kroodsmas, D.A., Block, B.A., Casagrandi, R., De Leo, G.A., Gatto, M., Micheli, F., McCauley, D.J., 2017. Assessing the effectiveness of a large marine protected area for reef shark conservation. *Biological Conservation* 207, 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.01.009>

- Wilhelm, T. 'Aulani, Sheppard, C.R.C., Sheppard, A.L.S., Gaymer, C.F., Parks, J., Wagner, D., Lewis, N., 2014. Large marine protected areas - advantages and challenges of going big: CONSIDERATIONS WHEN GOING BIG IN MPAs. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 24, 24–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2499>
- WWF. 2016. A Vision for Recapturing the Wealth of Tuna: Protecting habitats critical to tuna in the Coral Triangle. World Wildlife Fund, [online] http://d2ouvy59p0dg6k.cloudfront.net/downloads/factsheet_tuna_blueprint_hires.pdf.
- Young, H.S., Maxwell, S.M., Conners, M.G., Shaffer, S.A., 2015. Pelagic marine protected areas protect foraging habitat for multiple breeding seabirds in the central Pacific. *Biological Conservation* 181, 226–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.10.027>